

An approximation method to solve fractional Fredholm-Volterra integro-differential equations by Bernoulli polynomials

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, we introduce the Bernoulli operational matrix of Reimann-Liouville fractional integration. This matrix is used to approximate numerical solution of fractional-order Fredholm-Volterra integro-differential equations. Then the least square approximation method reduce the fractional integro - differential equations to systems of algebraic equations which are solved through the Newton's iterative method. The convergence of the method is discussed and finally, two numerical examples are presented to show the efficiency and accuracy of our method.

KEYWORDS: Bernoulli polynomials basis-Operational matrix-Convergence analysis-Fractional integro-differential equations-Least square approximation method.

1 INTRODUCTION

The fractional calculus has a long history from 30 September 1695, when the derivative of order $\gamma = \frac{1}{2}$ has been described by Leibniz. The theory of derivatives and integrals of non-integer order are stated in (Oldham,1974). The fractional differentiation for the mathematical modeling of real world physical problems has been used widely in recent years, for example, fractional calculus is used for modeling of earthquakes (He,1998), the modeling of earthquake, the fluid dynamic traffic model with fractional derivatives (He,1999), measurement of viscoelastic material properties (Bagley,Torvik,1983), etc. Derivatives of fractional order can be defined in different ways, e.g. Riemann-Liouville, Grunwald-Letnikov, and Caputo. In this paper we focus on Caputo derivative and Reimann-Liouville integration which turns out to be more useful in real life applications.

There have been several methods for the solution of fractional integro-differential equations, since it is relatively a new area in mathematics such as variation of parameters method (Boyadjiev et al.1998), Adomian decomposition method (ADM) (Momani, Noor,2006), (Ray, 2009), homotopy perturbation (Nawaz, 2011), CAS wavelet method (Saeedi et al. 2011) and Taylor expansion method (Huang et al. 2011), fractional differential transform method (FDTM) (Nazari, Shahmorad,2010) and the collocation

method (Rawashdeh,2006). The idea of this paper is to present some preliminaries and notations in the first section. In the next section Bernoulli operational matrix of the Reimann-Liouville fractional integration is introduced. We discuss the method convergence in section 4. Section 5 states the problem statement and finally section 6 contains some numerical examples. Section 7 will give a brief summary.

2 PRELIMINARIES AND NOTATIONS

In this section some basic definitions needed later in our discussion are recalled. Let us give the following definitions of left and right Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals, derivatives and Caputo fractional derivatives.

2.1 The fractional integral and derivative

Definition 1. The left and right Reimann-Liouville fractional integrals of order γ for a function $x: [a, b] \rightarrow R$ can be written as (Podlubny, 1999):

$$I_t^\gamma x(t) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\gamma)} \int_a^t (t - \tau)^{\gamma-1} x(\tau) d\tau,$$

$$I_b^\gamma x(t) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\gamma)} \int_t^b (\tau - t)^{\gamma-1} x(\tau) d\tau,$$

and the left and right Reimann-Liouville fractional derivatives are defined :

$$D_t^\gamma x(t) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(n - \gamma)} \left(\frac{d}{dt}\right)^n \int_a^t (t - \tau)^{n-\gamma-1} x(\tau) d\tau,$$

$$D_b^\gamma x(t) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(n - \gamma)} \left(-\frac{d}{dt}\right)^n \int_t^b (\tau - t)^{n-\gamma-1} x(\tau) d\tau.$$

Moreover, the left and right Caputo fractional derivatives are introduced as (Podlubny,1999):

$$D_t^\gamma x(t) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(n - \gamma)} \int_a^t (t - \tau)^{n-\gamma-1} x(\tau)^{(n)} d\tau,$$

$$D_b^\gamma x(t) = \frac{(-1)^n}{\Gamma(n - \gamma)} \int_t^b (\tau - t)^{n-\gamma-1} x(\tau)^{(n)} d\tau.$$

Where $\gamma > 0$ is a real number and $n = [\gamma]$ denotes the smallest integer greater than or equal to γ . The left Reimann- Liouville fractional integral has the following property.

$$I_t^\gamma t^n = \frac{\Gamma(n + 1)}{\Gamma(n + 1 + \gamma)} t^{n+\gamma}, \quad n > -1.$$

2.2 Bernoulli polynomials

Bernoulli polynomials of order m is defined on $[0, 1]$ as

$$\beta_m(t) = \sum_{i=0}^m \binom{m}{i} \alpha_{m-i} t^i. \quad (1)$$

Where $\alpha_i, i = 0, 1, \dots, m$, are Bernoulli numbers and defined as:

$$\frac{t}{e^t - 1} = \sum_{i=0}^m \alpha_i \frac{t^i}{i!}.$$

The first few Bernoulli numbers are

$$\alpha_0 = 1, \quad \alpha_1 = \frac{-1}{2}, \quad \alpha_2 = \frac{1}{6}, \quad \alpha_4 = \frac{-1}{30}, \dots,$$

with $\alpha_{2i+1}, i = 0, 1, 2, 3 \dots$

The first few Bernoulli polynomials are

$$\beta_0(t) = 1, \quad \beta_1(t) = t - \frac{1}{2}, \quad \beta_2(t) = t^2 - t + \frac{1}{6}, \dots$$

The following formula is satisfied for these polynomials (Arfken, 1985):

$$\int_0^1 \beta_n(t) \beta_m(t) dt = (-1)^{n-1} \frac{m! n!}{(m+n)!} \alpha_{n+m} \quad n, m \geq 1.$$

According to (Kreyszig, 1987), Bernoulli polynomials form a complete basis over the interval $[0, 1]$.

2.3 Function approximation

It is obvious that

$$Y = \text{span}\{\beta_0(t), \beta_1(t), \dots, \beta_m(t)\}$$

is a finite dimensional and closed subspace of the Hilbert space $H = L^2 [0; 1]$, also Y is a complete subspace and there is a unique best approximation out of Y such as $f_0(t) \in Y$ for each $f(t) \in H$, that is

$$\forall y(t) \in Y, \quad \|f(t) - f_0(t)\| \leq \|f(t) - y(t)\|.$$

Since $f_0(t) \in Y$ there exists unique coefficients c_0, c_1, \dots, c_m such that

$$f(t) \approx f_0(t) = \sum_{j=0}^m c_j \beta_j(t) = C^T \Psi(t).$$

Where T indicates transposition, C and $\Psi(t)$ are vectors given by:

$$C = [c_0, c_1, \dots, c_m]^T, \quad \Psi(t) = [\beta_0, \beta_1, \dots, \beta_m]^T. \quad (2)$$

And C is defined as

$$C = D^{-1} \langle f(t), \Psi(t) \rangle, \quad (3)$$

where \langle, \rangle denotes inner product and the entries of the matrix $D = (D_{i+1, j+1}), i, j = 0, \dots, m$ are given as follows:

$$D_{i+1,j+1} = \int_0^1 \beta_i(t)\beta_j(t) dt.$$

3 BERNOULLI OPERATIONAL MATRIX OF THE REIMANN-LIOUVILLE FRACTIONAL INTEGRATION

In this section we derive the $(m+1) \times (m+1)$ Reimann-Liouville fractional operational matrix of integration $F^{(\gamma)}$ expressed by (Keshavarz et al.,2015):

$$I_t^\gamma \Psi(t) = F^{(\gamma)} \Psi(t). \quad (4)$$

By using Eq. (1) and linearity of Reimann-Liouville fractional integral we have

$$\begin{aligned} I_t^\gamma \beta_i(t) &= I_t^\gamma \left(\sum_{r=0}^i \binom{i}{r} \alpha_{i-r} t^r \right) = \sum_{r=0}^i \binom{i}{r} \alpha_{i-r} I_t^\gamma t^r = \sum_{r=0}^i \binom{i}{r} \alpha_{i-r} \frac{\Gamma(r+1)}{\Gamma(r+1+\gamma)} t^{r+\gamma} \\ &= \sum_{r=0}^i b_{i,r} t^{r+\gamma}. \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Where

$$b_{i,r} = \binom{i}{r} \alpha_{i-r} \frac{\Gamma(r+1)}{\Gamma(r+1+\gamma)}.$$

now we can expand $t^{r+\gamma}$ in terms of Bernoulli polynomials as:

$$t^{r+\gamma} = \sum_{j=0}^m c_{r,j} \beta_j(t)$$

With

$$c_{r,j} = \frac{\langle t^{r+\gamma}, \beta_j(t) \rangle}{\langle \beta_j(t), \beta_j(t) \rangle}$$

and substitute in Eq.(5) we get

$$I_t^\gamma \beta_i(t) = \sum_{r=0}^i b_{i,r} \sum_{j=0}^m c_{r,j} \beta_j(t) = \sum_{j=0}^m \left(\sum_{r=0}^i b_{i,r} c_{r,j} \right) \beta_j(t). \quad (6)$$

Now let

$$\theta_{i,j,r} = b_{i,r} c_{r,j}$$

and rewrite Eq. (6) as

$$I_t^\gamma \beta_i(t) \approx \left[\sum_{r=0}^i \theta_{i,0,r}, \sum_{r=0}^i \theta_{i,1,r}, \dots, \sum_{r=0}^i \theta_{i,m,r} \right] \Psi(t) \quad i = 0, \dots, m.$$

Hence we have

$$\mathbf{F}^{(Y)} = \begin{bmatrix} \theta_{0,0,0} & \cdots & \theta_{0,m,0} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \sum_{r=0}^m \theta_{m,0,r} & \cdots & \sum_{r=0}^m \theta_{m,m,r} \end{bmatrix}.$$

4 CONVERGENCE ANALYSIS

In this section we show that the proposed approximation in equation (4) is valid, for this purpose we give the error vectors as follow:

$$E = I_t^Y \Psi(t) - \mathbf{F}^{(Y)} \Psi(t),$$

and show it tends to zero when the number of Bernoulli basis functions tends to infinity. To obtain this result we recall the following lemma and theorems.

Lemma 1. Suppose $f \in C^{m+1}[0; 1]$ and $Y = \text{span}\{\beta_0(t), \beta_1(t), \dots, \beta_m(t)\}$. Let y_0 be the best approximation for f out of Y then

$$\|f - y_0\|_{L^2[0;1]} \leq \frac{K}{(m+1)! \sqrt{2m+3}}$$

where $K = \text{Max}_{t \in [0,1]} |f^{(m+1)}(t)|$.

Proof. The set $\{1, t, \dots, t^m\}$ is a basis for polynomials space of degree m . We define

$$y_1(t) = f(0) + tf'(0) + \dots + \frac{t^m}{m!} f^{(m)}(0).$$

From Taylor expansion we have

$$|f(t) - y_1(t)| = \frac{f^{(m+1)}(\tau)t^{m+1}}{(m+1)!}$$

where $\tau \in (0, 1)$ Since y_0 is the best approximation $f(t)$ out of Y , $y_1(t) \in Y$ and from above equation, we have

$$\|f - y_0\|_{L^2[0;1]}^2 \leq \|f - y_1\|_{L^2[0;1]}^2 = \int_0^1 |f - y_1|^2 dt = \frac{K^2}{(m+1)!^2 (2m+3)}.$$

Then by taking square roots, the proof is complete.

Theorem 1. Suppose that H is a Hilbert space, Y is a finite dimensional closed subspace of H and $\{y_1, \dots, y_n\}$ is a basis for Y . Let x be an arbitrary element in H and y_0 be the unique best approximation to x out of Y . Then [15]

$$\|x - y_0\|_2^2 = \frac{G(x, y_1, \dots, y_n)}{G(y_1, \dots, y_n)},$$

where G is Gramian matrix.

Theorem 2. Suppose that $f \in L^2[0, 1]$ and $f(t)$ is approximated by $\sum_{i=0}^m c_i \beta_i(t)$ then we have (Kreyszig, 1987)

$$\lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} \|f(t) - \sum_{i=0}^m c_i \beta_i(t)\|_{L^2[0,1]} = 0.$$

Now by using these theorems we show that $(I_t^\gamma \beta_i(t) - \mathbf{F}^{(\gamma)} \beta_i(t))$ tends to zero. By considering $t^{r+\gamma} = \sum_{j=0}^m c_{r,j} \beta_j(t)$ and Theorem 1 we have

$$\left\| t^{r+\gamma} - \sum_{j=0}^m c_{r,j} \beta_j(t) \right\| = \left(\frac{G(t^{r+\gamma}, \beta_0, \beta_1, \dots, \beta_n)}{G(\beta_0, \beta_1, \dots, \beta_n)} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}.$$

So for $i = 0, 1, \dots, m$ we have

$$\begin{aligned} \left\| I_t^\gamma \beta_i(t) - \sum_{j=0}^m \left(\sum_{r=0}^i b_{i,r} c_{r,j} \right) \beta_j(t) \right\| &\leq \sum_{r=0}^i \frac{i! \alpha_{i-r}}{(i-r)! \Gamma(r+1+\gamma)} \left\| t^{r+\gamma} - \sum_{j=0}^m c_{r,j} \beta_j(t) \right\| \\ &\leq \sum_{r=0}^i b_{i,r} \left(\frac{G(t^{r+\gamma}, \beta_0, \beta_1, \dots, \beta_n)}{G(\beta_0, \beta_1, \dots, \beta_n)} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}. \end{aligned}$$

Now we can conclude by theorem 2 and the last inequality that the difference of $\mathbf{F}^{(\gamma)} \Psi(t)$ and $I_t^\gamma \Psi(t)$ tends to zero when the number of basis functions tends to infinity [16].

5 APPLICATIONS OF THE OPERATIONAL MATRIX OF FRACTIONAL INTEGRATION

Consider the following fractional integro-differential equation

$$D_t^\gamma x(t) = x(t) + g(t) + \int_0^t K_1(t, s) (x(s))^{n_1} (D_t^{\gamma_1} x(s))^{n_2} ds + \int_0^1 K_2(t, s) (x(s))^{n_3} (D_t^{\gamma_2} x(s))^{n_4} ds.$$

$$\text{Where } 0 \leq t, s \leq 1, \quad n-1 \leq \gamma \leq n, \quad 0 \leq \gamma_1 \leq \gamma_2 \leq \gamma. \quad (7)$$

And

$$x^{(i)}(0) = \vartheta_i \quad i = 0, 1, \dots, n-1, \quad (8)$$

we consider K_1 and K_2 as separable kernels and n_1, n_2, n_3, n_4 are positive integers and also all derivatives are Caputo fractional derivative. For solving $D_t^\gamma x(t)$ is approximated by the Bernoulli functions as

$$D_t^\gamma x(t) = \sum_{i=0}^m c_i \beta_i(t) = C^T \Psi(t), \quad (9)$$

where, vector $C = [c_0, c_1, \dots, c_m]^T$ is an unknown coefficient vector. By recalling the following property of Caputo derivative

$$I_t^\gamma D_t^\gamma x(t) = x(t) - \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} x^{(i)}(0) \frac{t^i}{i!},$$

we have

$$x(t) = \sum_{i=0}^m c_i I_t^\gamma \beta_i(t) + \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \vartheta_i \frac{t^i}{i!} = C^T \mathbf{F}^{(\gamma)} \Psi(t) + d^T \Psi(t), \quad (10)$$

also by considering the relation between Caputo derivative and Reimann-Liouville integration we can obtain

$$D_t^{\gamma_1} x(t) = C^T \mathbf{F}^{(\gamma-\gamma_1)} \Psi(t) + d_1^T \Psi(t), \quad (11)$$

$$D_t^{\gamma_2} x(t) = C^T \mathbf{F}^{(\gamma-\gamma_2)} \Psi(t) + d_2^T \Psi(t). \quad (12)$$

Now $K_1(t, s)$ and $K_2(t, s)$ are separated as follow

$$K_1(t, s) = A_1(t)B_1(s), \quad K_2(t, s) = A_2(t)B_2(s), \quad (13)$$

and we can write

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_0^t K_1(t, s) (x(s))^{n_1} (D_t^{\gamma_1} x(s))^{n_2} ds \\ & \approx A_1(t) \int_0^t B_1(s) \left(C^T \mathbf{F}^{(\gamma)} \Psi(s) + d^T \Psi(s) \right)^{n_1} \left(C^T \mathbf{F}^{(\gamma-\gamma_1)} \Psi(t) + d_1^T \Psi(t) \right)^{n_2} ds = H_1(t), \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

in the similar way we approximate

$$\int_0^1 K_2(t, s) (x(s))^{n_3} (D_t^{\gamma_2} x(s))^{n_4} ds \approx H_2(t).$$

now we substitute these approximation in equation (7) and get

$$C^T \Psi(t) - C^T \mathbf{F}^{(\gamma)} \Psi(t) - d^T \Psi(t) - g(t) - H_1(t) - H_2(t) = 0. \quad (15)$$

We consider functional J , as

$$J[c_0, c_1, \dots, c_m] = \int_0^1 (C^T \Psi(t) - C^T \mathbf{F}^{(\gamma)} \Psi(t) - d^T \Psi(t) - g(t) - H_1(t) - H_2(t))^2 dt \quad (16)$$

Now, we choose c_0, c_1, \dots, c_m to minimize J . The necessary conditions of optimization for the function (16), are

$$\frac{\partial J}{\partial c_k} = 0, \quad k = 0, 1, \dots, m. \quad (17)$$

These equations generate $m + 1$ nonlinear equations with $m + 1$ unknown coefficients, which can be solved using Newton's iterative method.

6 NUMERICAL EXAMPLES

In this section, we show the validity of the proposed method of section 5, with two examples.

Example 1

Consider the fractional-order Volterra integro-differential equation (Awawdeh et al.,2011)

$$\begin{aligned} D_t^{\frac{1}{2}} x(t) &= x(t) + \frac{8}{3\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2}\right)} t^{\frac{3}{2}} - t^2 - \frac{1}{3} t^3 + \int_0^t x(s) ds \quad 0 \leq t \leq 1 \\ x(0) &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

The exact solution of this problem is t^2 .

Table 1, shows the absolute errors between the exact and approximate solutions.

Table 1: The absolute errors for Example 1.

t	m=5	M=7
0.1	4.4×10^{-5}	6.9×10^{-6}
0.3	3.0×10^{-5}	9.9×10^{-7}
0.5	2.7×10^{-6}	9.7×10^{-7}
0.7	2.6×10^{-5}	9.2×10^{-7}
0.9	4.6×10^{-5}	1.0×10^{-5}

Example 2

Consider the following nonlinear fractional Fredholm integro-differential equation (Zhu, Fan,2012)

$$D_t^\gamma x(t) = 1 - \frac{t}{4} + \int_0^1 ts [x(s)]^2 ds \quad 0 \leq t \leq 1, \quad 0 \leq \gamma \leq 1$$

$$x(0) = 0 \tag{19}$$

The exact solution of this problem for $\gamma = 1$ is $x(t) = t$.

The absolute errors for $m = 2$ and 4 are shown in Table 2.

Table 2: The absolute errors for $\gamma = 1$ for Example 2.

t	m=2	M=4
0.1	3.1×10^{-13}	2.2×10^{-17}
0.3	9.3×10^{-13}	6.6×10^{-17}
0.5	1.5×10^{-12}	1.1×10^{-16}
0.7	2.1×10^{-12}	1.5×10^{-16}
0.9	2.7×10^{-12}	1.9×10^{-16}

7 CONCLUSION

In this paper, we introduce the Bernoulli operational matrix of Reimann-Liouville fractional integration by using this matrix and the least square approximation method the fractional-order Fredholm-Volterra integro-differential equations are reduced to systems of algebraic equations which are solved through the Newton's iterative method. The convergence of the method is discussed and finally, two numerical examples are presented to show the efficiency and accuracy of our method. The results are compared with exact solutions.

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